

Antarctic Research Trends Report 2025

Patterns and emerging trends in Antarctic and Southern Ocean academic publishing, 2016–2024

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PATTERNS AND EMERGING TRENDS IN ANTARCTIC AND SOUTHERN OCEAN ACADEMIC PUBLISHING 2016–2024

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FOREWORD

Planning for the Fifth International Polar Year (IPY5.net) 2032–33 is now well underway. Its goal is to address some of the most urgent global challenges by advancing polar research, with particular focus on the impacts of climate and ecosystem change in both the Arctic and the Antarctic.

This joint SCAR–UArctic study provides an important baseline of Antarctic research ahead of the next IPY. It offers a comprehensive overview of who holds and generates knowledge on the Antarctic and the Southern Ocean, and how these efforts have evolved over time. We are pleased to note the exceptionally high degree of international collaboration in Antarctic science—an essential foundation for maintaining strong, cooperative polar research globally.

The report presents a clear, evidence-based analysis of recent publishing patterns and their implications for research communities, scientific programs, and policy forums. It complements a similar study on Arctic research published last year. Together, these reports will be followed by a synthesis focusing on bipolar research, drawing on findings from both regions.

While SCAR and UArctic have supported this work, the views expressed herein are those of the authors. We wish to extend our gratitude to them for their rigorous and high-quality work, which provides invaluable insight into the current state of polar research worldwide.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The Antarctic and Southern Ocean Research Trends report aims to provide an understanding of recent scientific research trends and patterns in the region. Using peer-reviewed publications in the Scopus database as a proxy for scientific output, we examined scientific publications on Antarctic and Southern Ocean topics from 2016 to 2024, with a particular focus on the last three years.

The analysis revealed substantial variation in publication volume across individual countries and globally. The number of Antarctic and Southern Ocean publications peaked in 2021 and declined slightly each year through 2024. In 2024, China had the highest number of publications in quantity and quality, overtaking the United States in overall numbers in 2022 and in top-quartile publications in 2024. Of the top six countries in overall publications, all except China have seen a decline in numbers since 2016, including in top quartile publications.

Collaboration is a defining feature of Antarctic and Southern Ocean research, with international co-authorship occurring at a rate higher than the global average across all research fields. However, certain countries—most notably Russia, India, and China—show unusually low levels of international collaboration within ASO research. The US produces the highest number of internationally co-authored papers, though a greater proportion of these are bilateral collaborations compared to the more multilateral networks observed across other countries.

Between 2022 and 2024, the institutions with the highest number of ASO publications were the British Antarctic Survey, the Ministry of Natural Resources (China), the Russian Academy of Sciences, the University of Tasmania (Australia), the Chinese Academy of Sciences, and the Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (Argentina). The British Antarctic Survey, Chinese Academy of Sciences, and University of Tasmania—rank highest for top-quartile publications, together with the Alfred Wegener Institute (Germany) and Ocean University of China.

Finally, the field-weighted citation (i.e., the number of citations received by a publication, or set of publications, compared to the average number of citations received by similar publications) impact of ASO research has dropped from well above the global average in 2016 to below in 2023. Among the countries with high ASO output, the UK has the highest field-weighted citation impact.

While further research is required to understand the drivers of these trends, our findings are significant in suggesting a changing of the guard in national leadership and collaboration patterns in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research.

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1. INTRODUCTION

This report aims to understand recent trends in scientific research related to the Antarctic and Southern Ocean (ASO) region using peer-reviewed publications as a proxy for scientific output. As the West Antarctic region is rapidly warming and its ice shelves are destabilising, understanding the Antarctic environment is more critical than ever before. However, such research requires investment, both from states and individual institutions. In many disciplines, this research benefits from collaboration across national borders. Here, we report on scientific output, quality, degree of international co-authorship, and academic impact (in terms of citations) as a whole and by country, subject area, and institution between 2016 and 2024.

Information of this kind is essential for gauging the collective effort humans put into understanding the Antarctic region and how these efforts influence political decision-making. The 1959 Antarctic Treaty establishes the promotion of ‘international cooperation in scientific investigation in Antarctica’ as one of its key tenets.¹ Decision-making during Antarctic Treaty meetings is made by consensus among the Consultative Parties² – i.e., the 12 original nations from the 1959 treaty and nations that subsequently applied and were accepted as members.³ Application for Consultative status requires submitting evidence of ‘substantial scientific research’ in the region, such as a list of published international Antarctic-related studies.⁴ Even after becoming a Consultative Party, scientific output remains the currency for a nation’s presence on the continent and in decision-making forums.⁵ Such output also reflects (with some lag) a particular nation’s investment in the Antarctic and Southern Ocean region. The quantity of peer-reviewed publications is widely accepted as a proxy for

SCIENTIFIC OUTPUT REMAINS THE “CURRENCY OF CREDIBILITY” FOR STATES’ PRESENCE ON THE CONTINENT AND IN DECISION-MAKING FORUMS.

1. *Antarctic Treaty*, Preamble, Article II, Article III, Article IX.

2. At the time of writing (May 2025), Antarctic Treaty Consultative Parties comprised Argentina, Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Bulgaria, Chile, China, Czechia, Ecuador, Finland, France, Germany, India, Italy, Japan, Republic of Korea, Netherlands, New Zealand, Norway, Peru, Poland, Russian Federation, South Africa, Spain, Sweden, Ukraine, United Kingdom, United States, Uruguay.

3. *Antarctic Treaty*, Article IX.2

4. Hughes et al. 2024, p.3. As these authors point out, while the original Treaty text suggests that ‘the establishment of a scientific station or the dispatch of a scientific expedition’ as evidence of ‘substantial scientific research’, stations and expeditions are not necessarily prerequisites. For example, The Netherlands neither has stations nor conducts expeditions in the Antarctic but is a member.

5. Quilty 1990.

output.⁶ However, the quality of research is also an important consideration, which we examine here using top-quartile journals as our metric.

Unsurprisingly, several previous bibliometric analyses have examined the output of Antarctic-related research, some focusing on national contexts,⁷ disciplines, and topics, as well as others providing more general analyses.⁸ Data sources, temporal coverage, thematic parameters, and counting methods vary between these studies. The most recent general analysis spans the period from 2000 to 2019.⁹ Our report provides insight into the period since then, focusing on the direction of contemporary trends.

As we explain in more detail below, our data source, Scopus, is more effective at capturing the research outputs of the STEM disciplines than those of other disciplines. Although the Humanities, Arts, and Social Sciences (HASS) disciplines have actively conducted Antarctic research for decades, in, for example, international law, political science, and tourism studies, as well as recently emerging interest from disciplines such as Environmental History, Scopus's journal coverage, and therefore our report, does not include these disciplines in any meaningful way.¹⁰ Moreover, coverage of the humanities – a small but growing area within Antarctic research¹¹ – is even worse than that of the social sciences in Scopus. Similarly, Scopus poorly captures the creative arts, a non-traditional research output. Although these limitations are unlikely to significantly impact the findings of this report, given the dominance of STEM in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research, it is essential to understand that the results reported here do not accurately represent the contribution of the HASS disciplines to this field.

2. DATA AND METHODOLOGY

2.1 DATA SOURCES

This study gathers data from Scopus and SciVal, commonly used databases in bibliometric and research performance analysis. Scopus, a multidisciplinary bibliographic database, indexes peer-reviewed literature, including journals, conference proceedings, and books, across the sciences, social sciences, and humanities. It covers about 22,000 titles from approximately 5,000 interna-

6. Muntean 2025, p. 9.

7. E.g. González-Aravena et al 2023; Stefenon et al 2013; Zhang et al 2023; Liu et al 2017.

8. Ji et al 2014; Jang et al 2020; Wu et al 2022.

9. Wu et al 2022.

10. Singh (2021) reports that just over 88% of Scopus journal publications are in STEM areas and the rest in HASS – 9% in Social Sciences and less than 3% in Humanities and Creative Arts.

11. Roberts et al. 2016.

tional publishers. Geographically, Scopus aims for global representation, with approximately 20% of its titles published in languages other than English, as coverage extends to journals from all regions. Bibliographic records retrieved from Scopus were exported to SciVal for further analysis. SciVal, a web-based analytics platform, uses Scopus data to generate bibliometric indicators for research evaluation at the individual researcher, institution, and country levels. The bibliographic information and bibliometric indicators retrieved from SciVal and used in this study include Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), Source Normalised Impact per Paper (SNIP), and journal classifications as described below.

Scopus has limitations when used to determine global scholarly activity, as its coverage is biased toward journals from high-income regions, particularly North America and Europe; journals from Africa, parts of Asia, and lower-income countries are underrepresented.¹² Additionally, Scopus prioritises journal articles and therefore offers limited coverage of books and conference proceedings, underrepresenting disciplines where these types of publication are more common. These limitations should be taken into account when interpreting analyses based on Scopus data.

2.2 DEFINITION OF THE ANTARCTIC

The Antarctic is defined differently depending on the context. Politically, the Antarctic Treaty defines the Antarctic as the area south of 60° south latitude. The Convention on the Conservation of Antarctic Marine Living Resources, employing an ecosystem-based approach, defines the Antarctic region as the area with latitudes ranging from 45° to 60° south. The Antarctic Polar Front, where cold currents meet warmer northern waters, serves as a biophysical boundary; however, as currents are constantly changing, this boundary is also continually shifting. Moreover, this boundary is not necessarily reflected in bibliometric classifications. The boundaries of the Southern Ocean (SO) itself are contested, with the International Hydrographic Organisation setting its northern boundary at 60° south latitude. Still, some national traditions consider this ocean to extend to the southern coastlines of the circumpolar continents.¹³ Our approach is to be as inclusive as possible, so we incorporate research that includes the Antarctic continent and islands, the SO, and the sub-Antarctic islands.

THE ANTARCTIC IS DEFINED DIFFERENTLY DEPENDING ON THE CONTEXT — POLITICALLY, ECOLOGICALLY, AND SCIENTIFICALLY.

12. Maddi et al. 2025.

13. McCann 2018.

To reflect this breadth, while avoiding false positives to the greatest extent, we adopted the following search terms:

Topic Search (TS) = ((antarc* NOT (candida OR 'except antarctica' OR 'not antarctica' OR 'other than Antarctica')) OR 'transantarctic' OR 'ross sea' OR 'amundsen sea' OR 'weddell sea' OR 'southern ocean')

The search terms were recommended based on a study of polar bibliometrics and subsequently deployed in an analysis of how nations obtained consultative status under the Antarctic Treaty.¹⁴

2.3 METHODOLOGY

Counting methods

Counting methods are essential in bibliometrics as most publications have multiple authors. The primary question is how to attribute credit to individuals, institutions, or countries. Two common approaches are full counting (i.e., giving full and equal credit for publication to all contributors) and fractional counting (i.e., dividing the credit for each author by the number of authors).¹⁵ Fractional counting ensures that the total matches the actual number of publications.

This report primarily uses fractional counting. However, some figures also present full counts for complementary purposes. For articles involving multiple institutions or countries, fractional credit is assigned based on the number of participating entities.¹⁶ Analyses of international collaboration are based on full counting. This approach is consistent with standard practices such as those used in the National Science Foundation's (NSF's) Science and Engineering Indicators report.¹⁷ A limitation of the Scopus database is that a non-duplicative list of institutions or countries is reported for each publication rather than the institution or country for each author. Hence, the fractionalised counting reported here would differ in many cases from a counting based on individual author affiliations or countries.

Institutions

Figures for individual institutions are based on Scopus Affiliation Profiles created by standardising author affiliation data. Over 20,000 institutions are defined in the database. Although Scopus's disambiguation system precisely assigns publications to institutions, it may not capture all publications from an

14. Gray 2019; Hughes et al. 2024.

15. Gauffriau 2017.

16. When a publication has multiple country affiliations, each country receives a fractional contribution equal to one divided by the number of countries. The same method applies to institutions: each institution receives one divided by the total number of affiliated institutions.

17. National Science Board, National Science Foundation 2021.

institution. Therefore, institutional-level statistics should be interpreted with this limitation in mind.¹⁸

Field Classification

This study uses two field classification systems: the Australian and New Zealand Standard Research Classification (ANZSRC) and the All Science Journal Classification (ASJC). The ASJC system is more fine-grained and has a greater number of subject categories than the ANZSRC system, which comprises 27 top-level fields. Elsevier experts utilise ASJC classifications, which are based on a journal's aims, scope, and published content.

2.4 THE DATASET

We used Scopus using the above query, targeting document titles, abstracts, or keywords. The search was limited to research published between 2016 and 2024 and the following seven publication types: Article, Book, Chapter, Conference Paper, Letter, Note, and Review. The search yielded 29,831 documents, comprising 91% journal publications, 5% conference papers, and 4% books or book chapters.

We tested the precision of the query by having three expert raters evaluate the relevance of 300 randomly selected documents. The raters were instructed to classify each document into one of four categories: 'Not Relevant', 'Relevant Term'¹⁹, 'Partly Relevant Subject', and 'Relevant Subject'. These categories range from documents unrelated to Antarctica to those where Antarctica is the main subject. The raters' judgments showed some variation, particularly in the proportion of documents classified as relevant under stricter versus more inclusive criteria. On average, 3.9% of documents were judged Not Relevant, 20.7% Relevant Term, 26.8% Partly Relevant Subject, and 48.7% Relevant Subject. Fleiss' Kappa statistic was used to assess inter-rater reliability across the four categories, yielding a value of 0.638, indicating substantial agreement among the raters. A majority principle was used to summarise the results: the judgment of at least two raters determined a document's classification. This approach yielded a precision of 97% ($\pm 1\%$).

The dataset included publications from articles, reviews, conference papers, books, and book chapters. The selection method follows a similar approach to a previous report on Arctic research.²⁰

18. Donner et al. 2020.

19. 'Relevant term' means that the term Antarctic* or Southern Ocean was used positively and correctly but the article itself was not relevant. For example, an abstract might have a passing reference to the Southern Ocean but focuses on Africa.

20. Aksnes et al. 2023.

2.5 ANALYSES AND INDICATORS

The Field-Weighted Citation Impact

The Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI) in SciVal can be used to compare the number of citations of a publication with the global average of citations of similar publications (same year, type, and discipline). A score of 1.0 equals the world average. Above 1.0 means higher-than-average impact, and below 1.0 means lower-than-average impact. For example, 1.57 indicates that a publication had 57% more citations than the global average. Where we list them, FWCI scores for countries and institutions are given after averaging using fractional counting based on the number of affiliated entities. Articles from 2024 are not included in the citation analysis as these have not been available in the literature for a sufficiently long time to be cited.

International Collaboration

International Collaboration refers to articles co-authored by researchers affiliated with institutions in at least two countries.

Source Normalised Impact per Paper

Source Normalised Impact per Paper (SNIP), a field-normalised metric, measures a journal's citation impact by comparing the citations its articles receive to the expected citation rates in its subject field. SNIP is used in one of our analyses to identify publications in Q1 journals – those in the top 25th percentile by SNIP value. These journals typically represent the most influential and high-impact journals in their fields.

PHOTO CREDIT: FRASER KENNEDY.

3. ANALYSES OF ANTARCTIC RESEARCH

3.1 PUBLICATION OUTPUT: TOTAL AND BY COUNTRY

Publications across all nations were steady between 2016 and 2018, followed by an increase between 2019 and 2021 and a gradual but monotonic decline between 2022 and 2024 (Figure 3.1.1). The peak in publications in 2021 may reflect the near absence of Antarctic fieldwork during COVID, as researchers used this time to analyse previously collected data and write articles. Over this period, Antarctic publications decreased from 0.11% of all publications in all fields to 0.09%, suggesting that Antarctic research is growing more slowly than the average for all research fields.

Figure 3.1.1. Number of Antarctic publications by year between 2016 and 2024.

Between 2022 and 2024, China-based researchers surpassed their US-based counterparts in terms of fractional contributions to Antarctic publications, at 16.8% and 15%, respectively (Figure 3.1.2). At a much lower volume, the next nations were the UK (6.9%), Australia (5.5%), Germany (4.7%), Russia (3.9%), and Italy (3.3%). Several non-Consultative Parties and non-signatory nations made lower fractional contributions, ranging from 0.8% to 3.3%, but these contributions significantly impacted the total number of publications. More than 100 countries contributed to the 'Other countries' total, notably including Denmark (75 publications) and Turkey (65), both Antarctic Treaty signatories.

Notably, all the top 25 countries except Canada are Consultative Parties (decision-making nations) to the Antarctic Treaty. Canada’s output, as judged by publications in Scopus, is higher than that of many existing Consultative parties.

Compared to previous analyses of Antarctic literature, the most significant change in our publication dataset is the inclusion of publications from China. Previous general bibliometric analyses of Antarctic research found the US to have the highest overall output. The most recent study we are aware of, which examines the period from 2000 to 2020, ranks the US first, followed by the UK, Australia, Germany, and France, with China in seventh place.²¹ Our findings also show that the US, UK, Australia, and Germany were among the top five countries, in the same order as the earlier study. However, during our study period, China was ranked first, rather than seventh place.

Figure 3.1.2. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised) by country, total 2022–2024. The 25 nations with the largest number of publications are listed.

21. Wu et al. 2022.

Focusing on the six leading Antarctic countries by fractionalised publication volume highlights substantial trends over the study period that reflect the changes in the highest output in the recent three-year period described above. Aside from the 2020–2021 COVID-19 surge, US fractionalised publications declined approximately 20% during the study period (Figure 3.1.3). By contrast, China’s fractionalised publications increased dramatically during the study period, overtaking the US as the most prolific publisher of papers in 2022 and nearly tripling by 2024.²² The other four leading nations exhibit an overall decrease, with a ~30% monotonic decline evident for Australia since its 2019 peak. Russia experienced a notable increase in publications between 2020 and 2023, followed by a significant decrease in 2024.

CHINA’S FRACTIONALISED PUBLICATIONS HAVE INCREASED DRAMATICALLY SINCE 2017, NEARLY TRIPLING BY 2024.

Fractionalised publications (Figure 3.1.3a) and full-counting publications (Figure 3.1.3b) exhibited similar broad patterns, but some countries shifted position relative to one another. Russia is included in the top six countries in the fractionalised analysis (Figure 3.1.3a) but is replaced by France in the full-counting analysis (Figure 3.1.3b). The other top five countries were the same. The dramatic rise in full-counting publications from China has not yet seen its output surpass that of the US, despite the latter’s clear decline in total publication count. Regarding full-counting publications, Australia and Germany are much closer to one another than is observed in the fractionalised data (Figure 3.1.3a). Post-COVID declines are mainly evident for the US, Australia, and Germany, while the UK and France have largely maintained their previous total publication rates. Russia’s publication output dropped by nearly 50% between 2023 and 2024, possibly reflecting the impact of international sanctions and decreased funding for research.

22. The strong growth in China’s scientific output is a general trend; that is, it is not unique to Antarctic research. In 2016, China surpassed the US to become the world’s leading producer of scientific publications across all fields (Tollefson 2018). In Antarctic research, however, this shift occurred later when measured by fractional publication counts (Figure 3.1.3a).

Figure 3.1.3a. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised) by year for the largest countries in terms of publication output, 2016–2024

Figure 3.1.3b. Number of Antarctic publications (full counting) by year for the six largest countries in terms of (full count) publication output, 2016–2024. Note that different countries are listed from those in Figure 3.1.3a.

Given the high degree of cooperation among European countries in Antarctic research, we also present the results of grouping European countries (Figure 3.1.4). The EU/EEA produces more publications than the USA or China, a trend that has been maintained after Brexit. A comparison of full-counting and fractionalised publications suggests that some countries are more collaborative, and the collaboration rates changed over the study period. We return to this in Section 3.5.

Figure 3.1.4. Annual fractionalised publications by European nations over time. European Union (EU) and European Economic Area (EEA) country groupings are shown. UK publications are listed separately after Brexit. Time series of publications from the US and China are shown for comparison.

3.2 PUBLICATION OUTPUT: BY QUARTILE, TOTAL AND BY COUNTRY

Not all publication outlets are of equal quality, so we explore the distribution of journal publications based only on the ranking (SNIP) quartile of the journal. During our study period, most journal publications in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research were published in first-quartile (Q1) journals, and relatively few were published in journals in the lower two quartiles (Figure 3.2.1). Our data shows that Antarctic research tended to be published in high-impact journals. In total, 52% of Antarctic research published between 2022 and 2024 appeared in Q1 journals, whereas 25% of all research fields published between 2022 and 2024 appeared in Q1 journals, suggesting that publications in Antarctic research were published in higher-than-average quality journals across all countries.

However, there is substantial variation by country regarding Q1 publication rates (Figure 3.2.2). Of the leading six nations, the US, UK, Australia, and Germany published on average approximately 65% of their publications in Q1 journals between 2022 and 2024. China had a lower rate of publication in Q1 journals, 51%. The leading countries in Q1 publication rates were Switzerland and Finland, with more than 75% of their relatively small number of publications in Q1 journals. Meanwhile, Russia had the lowest rate of Q1 publications, 14%, with Brazil, Argentina, India, and the Czech Republic also notably lower than average. As non-English journals often have lower impact factors, a country’s lower Q1 ratio may result from a preference for publishing in native-language journals. Again, Canada’s position in 13th place – and as the only non-Consultative Party in the top 20 – is relevant considering its recent application for Consultative status.

ANTARCTIC RESEARCH TENDS TO BE PUBLISHED IN HIGH-IMPACT JOURNALS — OVER TWICE THE GLOBAL AVERAGE.

Figure 3.2.1. Proportion of Antarctic publications 2022–2024 by SNIP quartile categories.

Figure 3.2.2. Number of Antarctic top quartile (Q1) publications by country 2022-2024, fractionalised (left axis) and proportion (ratio) of top quartile publications (right axis).

Trends are also evident in the publication rate in Q1 journals for the most prolific six nations (Figure 3.2.3). The ordering and trends are broadly similar to those for all publication types (Figure 3.1.3a). As was the case for all publications, strong declines are evident in US Q1 publications (27% overall reduction) as well as for Germany, France, and Australia since 2021 (50%, 39% and 35%, respectively).

CLIMATE AND CLIMATE CHANGE-RELATED TOPICS DOMINATE ANT-ARCTIC RESEARCH.

Figure 3.2.3. Number of Antarctic top-quartile publications, Q1 (fractionalised) by year for the largest countries in terms of publication output, 2016-2024

3.3 PUBLICATION OUTPUT BY SUBJECT AREA

Unsurprisingly, Antarctic and Southern Ocean research is dominated by the sciences (Figure 3.3.1), a finding that reflects the goal of the Antarctic Treaty. However, our dataset is biased against HASS subjects. Among the sciences, the dominant subject area is Earth Sciences, accounting for almost one-third of the total publications, which aligns with the earlier study of publications between 2000 and 2020.²³ Approximately 20% of publications were in biological sciences. Multidisciplinary sciences encompass some of the most high-profile publications, including those featured in the leading journals *Nature* and *Science*. Still, this category is not restricted to such journals. No other subject area contributes more than 10% of total publications. Of the HASS subjects, ‘History’, ‘Heritage’, and ‘Archaeology’ are the most prominent in our database, followed by ‘Human Society’.

²³. Wu et al. 2022.

However, the database’s definition of ‘Earth Sciences’ is broad and includes, e.g., oceanography, atmospheric science, glaciology, and solid earth science. In contrast, ‘Biological Sciences’ include ecology, animal behaviour, and marine biology. Figure 3.3.2 shows a more detailed characterisation of the sciences, revealing a broad spread of topics led by Oceanography, Earth and Planetary Sciences, and Evolution, Behaviour, and Systematics.

Figure 3.3.1. Proportion of total Antarctic publication output by discipline/field (ANZSRC categories), total 2022–2024

Figure 3.3.2. Number of Antarctic publications by All Science Journal Classification (ASJC) fields (largest), total 2022–2024

A word cloud analysis of topics suggests that climate and climate change-related topics, including sea level, land ice, and the Last Glacial Maximum, were the most prominent (Figure 3.3.2). In biology, phytoplankton research was most prominent, and studies on carbon dioxide were common, presumably across atmospheric sciences and the uptake of carbon dioxide by the ocean and marine life. The only keywords related to the HASS disciplines were ‘sovereignty’, ‘international politics’, and possibly ‘China’, indicating the prevalence of governance, geopolitics, and law in Antarctic-related research in those disciplines.

Figure 3.3.2. Most frequently appearing topics in the Antarctic publications, 2016–2024, as a word cloud. The two most frequently appearing phrases, “Antarctic Region” and “Southern Ocean”, have been removed.

3.4 PUBLICATION OUTPUT BY INSTITUTION

Separating publications between 2022 and 2024 by contributing institution (Table 3.4.1; Table A2; full period Table A1) shows that the British Antarctic Survey (BAS, UK) was the most prolific institution regarding fractionalised publications. Although having a much smaller number of fractionalised publications, CNRS (France) had the highest number of full-count publications. This finding suggests that CNRS was frequently part of large teams of multi-institutional researchers. Following BAS in terms of fractionalised publications was the Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China (China) and the Russian Academy of Sciences.

The leading university by both counts was the University of Tasmania (Australia), with more than twice the publication counts of any other university globally. Oceans University of China was the second highest in fractionalised counts, and the University of Colorado Boulder was the highest in full counting.

Despite being one of the top two leading publishing nations for Antarctic research, the USA does not have any institutions in the top 10 institutions globally in terms of either fractionalised or full counting. This finding reflects a highly distributed funding model in the US, which supports a wide range of universities and government institutions across the country.

Table 3.4.2 lists the institutions according to Q1 journal publication statistics, showing only the largest institutions (a complete listing is provided in Table A3). BAS remains the leading institution globally regarding the number of fractionalised publications between 2022 and 2024, with 40% more fractionalised publications than the second-ranked Chinese Academy of Sciences. Again, CNRS had the most significant number of full-counting Q1 publications despite having a relatively low number of fractionalised Q1 publications. Despite the prominence of the Russian Academy of Sciences in terms of total publications (Table 3.4.1), no Russian organisations are listed in Table 3.4.1.

The University of Tasmania was again the leading university in fractionalised and full-counting Q1 publications. Of the institutions shown, Princeton University had the highest publishing rate in Q1 journals in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research (89%), although with a modest volume. A noticeably high publishing rate in Q1 journals is evident at the US universities listed, with rates commonly exceeding 70%.

Several government institutions had lower rates of publishing in Q1 journals, which may reflect their role in undertaking applied or policy-relevant research. Likewise, some universities and other organisations will have lower rates of Q1 publications when they have a broad remit in both applied and fundamental research across a wide range of subjects.

Table 3.4.1. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised and full counts) for the 20 largest* institutions in terms of publication output. Total figures for 2022–2024.

INSTITUTION	COUNTRY	NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS (FRACTIONALISED)	NUMBER OF PUBLICATIONS (FULL COUNTING)
British Antarctic Survey	UK	169.7	640
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People’s Republic of China	China	154.3	398
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	135.8	333
University of Tasmania	Australia	126.4	418
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	122.9	536
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	112.1	347
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	96.7	270
Ocean University of China	China	96.7	185
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Germany	89.5	380
CNRS	France	86.0	664
Shanghai Ocean University	China	81.2	129
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	64.8	75
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	63.4	219
Polar Research Institute of China	China	63.2	200
Tongji University	China	60.3	120
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	59.2	219
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	56.8	252
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	55.2	217
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	54.8	229

* For a more comprehensive list of institutions, see Appendix Table A2.

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Table 3.4.2. Number of top-quartile Antarctic publications (Q1) (fractionalised and full counts) for the 20 largest* institutions in publication output. Total figures for 2022–2024.

INSTITUTION	COUNTRY	NUMBER OF ARTICLES (FRACTIONALISED)	NUMBER OF ARTICLES (FULL COUNTING)	Q1 RATIO
British Antarctic Survey	UK	101.2	403	0.61
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	71.7	345	0.60
University of Tasmania	Australia	68.6	270	0.61
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Rep of China	China	68.5	214	0.47
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Germany	63.5	278	0.72
Ocean University of China	China	50.6	115	0.53
CNRS	France	48.7	436	0.58
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	46.0	144	0.48
University of California at San Diego	USA	44.9	173	0.88
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	41.4	190	0.74
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	40.7	169	0.74
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	36.3	131	0.60
University of Washington	USA	35.7	124	0.77
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	35.0	38	0.55
University of New South Wales	Australia	33.8	109	0.82
CSIRO	Australia	33.0	138	0.69
Columbia University	USA	32.8	129	0.82
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	32.2	143	0.60
Southern Marine Science and Engineering Guangdong Laboratory - Guanzhou	China	30.2	107	0.71
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	29.2	135	0.56

* For a more comprehensive list of institutions, see Appendix Table A3.

3.5 INTERNATIONAL COLLABORATION

One measure of international collaboration in research is co-authorship of publications. This is particularly prominent in the sciences and can be less pronounced in some HASS disciplines due to traditions of sole authorship. Figure 3.5.1 shows Antarctic publications categorised by the number of nations involved during the study period. Approximately 55% of all published research involves a single nation.

Approximately 45% of all published Antarctic and Southern Ocean research involves collaboration with one or more nations, which is five percentage points higher than the rate reported by a previous study (using the Web of Science as a data source) for 2015.²⁴ This figure remained relatively stable over the study period, in contrast to the continuous increase observed in earlier studies.²⁵

24. Jang et al. 2015.

25. Jang et al. 2015.

This rate of international collaboration is significantly more than the rate for the full Scopus database for articles and conference papers in science and engineering fields, which in 2020 was just under 25%.²⁶ This difference indicates the cooperative nature of much Antarctic research. As previous researchers have suggested, the higher rate of co-authorship between countries in Antarctic research likely reflects the expense and logistical difficulties of conducting research in remote and extreme environments. That is, research projects are more viable if supported by more than one nation.²⁷ However, the plateauing of this figure during the nine years observed in this report, in contrast to earlier decades, suggests that a ceiling may have been reached.

Figure 3.5.1. Antarctic publications by type of international collaboration, 2016–2024.

26. National Science Board, National Science Foundation. 2021. This report suggests that international cooperation had been increasing, in comparison to the stability in Antarctic cooperative research seen in Figure 3.5.1.

27. Jang et al. 2015.

ANTARCTIC RESEARCH REMAINS ONE OF THE MOST INTERNATIONALLY COLLABORATIVE SCIENTIFIC FIELDS IN THE WORLD.

There is significant variation in international collaboration by country (Figures 3.5.2 and 3.5.3). The most frequent collaborators, with rates of nearly 90%, were France, Canada, Norway, and the Netherlands. The lowest collaboration rates were with

China, India, Russia, and, to a lesser extent, South Korea. These low rates may relate in part to fluency in a common language.

Regarding modes of collaboration, the relatively low rate of multilateral collaborations by US institutions (Figure 3.5.4) is noteworthy, as it has a multilateral collaboration rate similar to that of Brazil and Argentina. The low rate of multilateral collaboration among US researchers requires further exploration, but it may be related to the prevalence of large bilateral research programs. The nation’s most frequent multilateral collaborations were with The Netherlands, South Africa, Norway, New Zealand, Spain, and France.

Figure 3.5.5 illustrates the breakdown of collaboration modes by science subject. Global and Planetary Change, Palaeontology, and Multidisciplinary Sciences have the highest rate of multilateral collaborations, as expressed in co-authorship. Ecology is the most unilateral subject area listed.

Figure 3.5.2. Number of publications and proportion of international collaboration by country, total 2022–2024. Only the 20 leading countries are listed.

Figure 3.5.3. Proportion of international co-authorship and total number of Antarctic publications fractionated by country (2022–2024). Only the 20 leading countries are listed.*

* China (CHN), USA (USA), UK (GBR), Australia (AUS), Germany (DEU), Russia (RUS), Italy (ITA), India (IND), Brazil (BRA), France (FRA), Japan (JPN), South Korea (KOR), Chile (CHL), Argentina (ARG), Spain (ESP), New Zealand (NZL), Canada (CAN), South Africa (ZAF), Norway (NOR), Netherlands (NLD).

Figure 3.5.4. International collaboration by country. Only the 20 leading countries are listed. Proportions by collaboration type, 2022–2024.*

* Collaboration rates are generally much higher at the country level than measured at the overall global level. This is because articles with international collaboration are counted once for each contributing country when reported at the individual country level, while they are not multiplied when counted globally.

Figure 3.5.5. International collaboration by science subject in terms of ASJC-fields (largest). Proportions by collaboration type, 2022–2024.

Figure 3.5.6 visualises international collaboration and its volume. The size of each circle represents the number of internationally collaborative articles produced by that country. The width of the lines connecting the circles indicates the volume of collaboration between countries, measured by the number of co-authored articles. The distance between the circles reflects the relative intensity of collaboration: countries with stronger collaborative ties – i.e., relatively high numbers of joint publications – are positioned closer together. This arrangement allows for identifying clusters of countries that collaborate more closely with each other, highlighted by different colours.

Among the major publishing nations, the US collaborated most frequently with the UK, China, and Australia, with fewer collaborations with Germany. Despite its relatively small volume of publications, Canada had relatively high collaboration rates with US researchers.

The UK collaborated most with the US, followed by Germany, Australia, and France. Australia collaborated with China as much as with New Zealand, but primarily with the US and UK in similar measures. New Zealand had a relatively high collaboration rate with US researchers, likely due to shared field logistics and proximity to field stations.

Figure 3.5.6. Graphical illustration of international research collaboration, based on bilateral and trilateral publications 2022–2024*. The meaning of the lines, circles and their relative spacing are described in text.

* Limited to countries contributing to at least 100 Antarctic publications during the period. Software source: VOSviewer, <https://www.vosviewer.com>.

The heatmap, Table 3.5.1, visualises the collaboration networks between countries, using a colour scale to indicate the intensity of collaboration. The intensity is measured by the proportion of internationally co-authored articles shared between countries. Only the largest countries are shown in the number of published articles.

To interpret the heatmap, it is essential to read it **from left to right, column** by column. Each column represents the collaboration profile of a specific country – that is, how strongly other countries collaborate with that country in relative terms.

For example, New Zealand shows strong collaboration with Australia, whereas Australia's collaboration with New Zealand appears less intense. This asymmetry occurs because the absolute number of co-authored articles between the two countries is the same. Still, Australia produced a much larger volume of internationally co-authored papers overall. As a result, Australia represents a larger share of New Zealand's international collaborations than New Zealand does of Australia's.

PHOTO CREDIT: PETE HARMSEN/AAD.

Table 3.5.1. Heat map matrix showing country-to-country relative collaboration intensity based on bilateral and trilateral relative terms. Only the 20 leading publishing nations are shown.

COLLABORATING COUNTRY	COUNTRY									
	Argentina	Australia	Brazil	Canada	Chile	China	France	Germany	India	
	Argentina	0.01	0.01	0.07	0.01	0.09	0.00	0.03	0.05	0.01
	Australia	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.10	0.05	0.02
	Brazil	0.07	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.07	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.02
	Canada	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.04	0.03	0.00
	Chile	0.11	0.01	0.07	0.07	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.03	0.00
	China	0.01	0.10	0.01	0.11	0.01	0.01	0.05	0.08	0.01
	France	0.05	0.06	0.03	0.06	0.06	0.01	0.01	0.06	0.02
	Germany	0.11	0.04	0.04	0.06	0.06	0.03	0.09	0.01	0.03
	India	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.01
	Italy	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.07	0.07	0.00
	Japan	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.02	0.02
	Netherlands	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02	0.01
	New Zealand	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.05	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00
	Norway	0.00	0.03	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.03
	Russia	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00
	South Africa	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.02	0.02	0.00
	South Korea	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.01	0.02
	Spain	0.08	0.01	0.04	0.01	0.10	0.00	0.03	0.03	0.01
UK	0.03	0.13	0.06	0.09	0.08	0.03	0.16	0.18	0.03	
USA	0.09	0.19	0.14	0.38	0.15	0.11	0.19	0.18	0.05	

1 publications, 2022-2024. The table should be read column-wise, indicating how strongly other countries collaborate in

COUNTRY

Italy	Japan	Netherlands	New Zealand	Norway	Russia	South Africa	South Korea	Spain	UK	USA
0.01	0.00	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.08	0.01	0.01
0.02	0.08	0.05	0.20	0.10	0.00	0.07	0.02	0.03	0.09	0.07
0.01	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.00	0.06	0.00	0.04	0.02	0.03
0.01	0.02	0.02	0.05	0.04	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.05
0.02	0.03	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.12	0.03	0.03
0.03	0.07	0.07	0.02	0.06	0.04	0.02	0.05	0.02	0.06	0.11
0.06	0.03	0.08	0.04	0.05	0.01	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.07	0.04
0.10	0.04	0.07	0.05	0.08	0.03	0.07	0.03	0.06	0.12	0.06
0.00	0.02	0.01	0.00	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01
	0.06	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.05	0.05	0.04
0.04		0.02	0.01	0.03	0.01	0.04	0.03	0.01	0.02	0.03
0.01	0.01		0.02	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.03	0.02
0.02	0.01	0.03		0.05	0.00	0.02	0.03	0.03	0.04	0.04
0.01	0.02	0.03	0.04		0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.02
0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.03		0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	0.00
0.01	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.02	0.00		0.00	0.01	0.05	0.01
0.01	0.02	0.02	0.03	0.01	0.00	0.00		0.01	0.01	0.03
0.03	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.02	0.01	0.02	0.01		0.02	0.01
0.10	0.04	0.17	0.13	0.16	0.01	0.23	0.02	0.08		0.13
0.17	0.17	0.21	0.27	0.16	0.02	0.14	0.17	0.09	0.25	

3.6 CITATION IMPACT

The average Field-Weighted Citation Impact (FWCI), a measurement of citation rates of individual publications relative to their field of research, for Antarctic research published between 2016 and 2023, reveals that global Antarctic research was more frequently cited than the average before 2021 and less frequently cited than the average after 2021 (Figure 3.6.1). This finding is surprising, as there appears to be no apparent reason within Antarctic research to explain it. However, a similar pattern was also observed for Arctic research.²⁸ Further exploration of the six leading publishing nations reveals that the UK, Germany, and, to a lesser extent, Australia and Russia have experienced a significant decline in FWCI over the same period, contributing to the global change in FWCI. Many countries exhibited a shift in average FWCI between the period 2016–2019 and 2020–2023 (Figure 3.6.2). This finding suggests that the drop in average FWCI was widespread, especially among nations with high FWCI. However, there were three exceptions to this trend: New Zealand’s average FWCI increased substantially, and India’s and China’s average FWCI increased marginally.

Figure 3.6.1. Field-Weighted Citation Impact for Antarctic research total for the six largest countries, 2016–2023.

²⁸ Aksnes et al. 2023.

Before 2020, China’s FWCI increased; however, since 2020, China’s FWCI has remained steady and is currently well below average (Figure 3.6.1). This lower-than-average FWCI, combined with the rapid increase in Antarctic publications from China since 2017, may add to the reduction in overall Antarctic FWCI since 2020 (noting FWCI lags publications by two years).

Figure 3.6.2. Field-Weighted Citation Impact for Antarctic research, for the largest countries in publication output, 2016–2019 and 2020–2023.

According to FWCI data, US institutions dominated the highest FWCI institutions, essentially government-funded space and research centres (Table 3.6.1). Some smaller volume nations had very high average FWCI, where the overall highest FWCI institute was the University of Utrecht (The Netherlands), followed by the University of NSW (Australia) (Table A4). The Universidad de Chile (Chile) was notable as the sole South American institution in the top ten highest FWCI institutions.

GLOBAL ANTARCTIC RESEARCH WAS MORE HEAVILY CITED THAN AVERAGE BEFORE 2021, BUT SWIFTLY BECAME LESS FREQUENTLY CITED THEREAFTER.

At the lower end of FWCI are institutions in Russia and China. China, in the lower end, is somewhat surprising given the high rate of Q1 publishing from China-based researchers. This requires further exploration, but could result from lower visibility of this research, lesser familiarity with emerging researchers producing it, lower rates of collaboration with other highly publishing nations, or a perceived lower quality of this research.

Table 3.6.1. Leading institutions sorted by field-weighted citation impact, with their publications (fractionalised) and field-weighted citation impact, for the 20 largest* institutions in terms of publication output, 2020-2023.

Institution	Country	Number of articles (fractionalised)	Field-weighted citation impact
University of Washington	USA	70.7	1.64
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	83.1	1.55
British Antarctic Survey	UK	238.5	1.37
University of California at San Diego	USA	78.2	1.33
University of Tasmania	Australia	175.2	1.21
CNRS	France	126.4	1.21
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	78.4	1.11
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	91.3	1.11
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Germany	143.4	1.10
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	159.7	0.83
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	76.7	0.82
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	157.6	0.78
Ocean University of China	China	119.2	0.77
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China	China	177.5	0.59
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	128.5	0.57
Polar Research Institute of China	China	75.8	0.50
Shanghai Ocean University	China	100.8	0.49
St. Petersburg State University	Russia	70.1	0.49
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	207.1	0.46
Wuhan University	China	72.4	0.43

* For a more comprehensive list of institutions, see Appendix Table A4.

4. CONCLUSIONS AND MAIN FINDINGS

We examined Antarctic and Southern Ocean publications from 2016 to 2024 in the Scopus database. The total number of publications peaked in 2021, presumably due to COVID-19 restrictions, and then declined slightly every year until the end of the study period, 2024.

During the study period, China surpassed the US as the leading publisher of Antarctic and Southern Ocean research in terms of quantity and quality (top-quartile journal) publications, overtaking the US in 2022 and 2024, respectively. This finding contrasts with the steady decline in publications in the database from the other leading nations, notably the US, Germany, Australia, and the UK. Although Russia had a high number of total publications, its publication numbers in the top-quartile journals were comparatively minimal. These results may indicate a changing of the guard in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research.

International collaboration, a hallmark of Antarctic research, remained steady throughout the study period, despite substantial variations between nations. We found variations between levels of bilateral and multilateral cooperation

between countries. For example, China, India, and Korea had notably lower rates of international co-authorship, suggesting that this may be related to common language challenges.

Regarding individual institutions, the British Antarctic Survey was the global leader in total and top-quartile publications. The UK had the highest FWCI overall, although many individual US institutions also rated highly. The University of Tasmania was the leading university globally regarding Antarctic and Southern Ocean publications.

The prominence of Canada in the statistics is noteworthy, given that Canada is not a Consultative member of the Antarctic Treaty. Canada's volume and quality of its scientific output during the study period are comparable or higher than those of many other nations with Consultative status.

We focused on contributions to publications regardless of the authorship role in the publication. For example, we did not assess research leadership, as may be indicated by first or, in some fields, senior authorship. That is, we did not explore intellectual leadership in Antarctic and Southern Ocean research despite it being highly relevant to credibility in the Antarctic Treaty System and worthy of future study.

Our study examines the trends and patterns in Antarctic and Southern Ocean publications, but understanding their drivers requires further analysis and study. For example, future studies should investigate the relatively low citation rates of papers from China despite the rapidly growing rate of China's publications in top-quartile journals.

Finally, our analysis is constrained by the Scopus database's science focus, so more research is needed that explores the trends and patterns in humanities, arts, and social science publications.

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Author contributions

Lars Kullerud at the UArctic and KL conceived the study, while KL lead the study. RD designed and implemented the Scopus search, with guidance from KL, EL, and MAK. DWA performed the statistical analyses and prepared the figures and tables. EL reviewed relevant literature. MAK, EL, DWA, and RD drafted the manuscript, and all authors provided comments.

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APPENDIX

Table A1. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised and full counting) by institution, total 2016-2024 and sorted by fractionalised counting. Only the largest institutions, in terms of publication output (fractionalised counts), are listed.

Institution	Country	Number of publications (fractionalised)	Number of publications (full counting)
British Antarctic Survey	UK	561.5	1905
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	378.9	915
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Germany	364.2	1490
University of Tasmania	Australia	348.6	1224
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	327.8	1025
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China	China	320.7	805
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	298.7	1243
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	291.9	779
CNRS	France	283.2	2135
Ocean University of China	China	217.0	395
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	194.1	760
University of California at San Diego	USA	180.7	663
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	180.0	670
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	173.6	731
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	169.8	575
Shanghai Ocean University	China	169.3	271
CSIRO	Australia	167.9	815
Columbia University	USA	163.0	613
University of Washington	USA	159.7	543
Wuhan University	China	158.1	272
University of New South Wales	Australia	136.2	457
Polar Research Institute of China	China	131.9	408
University of Bremen	Germany	129.1	520
Institut de recherche pour le développement	France	125.7	1296
CSIC	Spain	124.2	670
University of Otago	New Zealand	122.1	345
Tongji University	China	121.1	230
St. Petersburg State University	Russia	119.0	246
University of Cambridge	UK	116.4	417
Australian National University	Australia	114.8	369
National Centre for Antarctic & Ocean Research	India	111.4	294
University of Canterbury	New Zealand	110.8	275
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	110.3	456
Universidade de São Paulo	Brazil	109.1	307
University of Cape Town	South Africa	107.2	316
Research Organisation of Information and Systems, National Institute of Polar Research	Japan	105.8	465

California Institute of Technology	USA	102.3	450
Utrecht University	Netherlands	101.7	411
Masaryk University	Czech Republic	100.0	207
NIWA	New Zealand	98.0	347
University of Southampton	UK	96.2	489
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	91.8	108
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	USA	91.7	392
National Center for Atmospheric Research	USA	89.9	366
Universidad de Magallanes	Chile	89.4	315
Universidad de Concepción	Chile	89.4	327
University of Melbourne	Australia	88.3	248
Universidad Austral de Chile	Chile	88.0	266
Monash University	Australia	87.5	251
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina	86.1	287
Universidad de Chile	Chile	85.2	299
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	USA	80.3	340
Ohio State University	USA	79.6	321
National Oceanography Centre	UK	76.3	411
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA	75.3	292
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Argentina	75.0	243
Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology	Japan	74.8	294
University of Pretoria	South Africa	74.6	211
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	Ukraine	74.6	205
Lomonosov Moscow State University	Russia	73.5	171
United States Department of Energy	USA	71.4	440
Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology	USA	70.8	355
Ministry of Earth Sciences	India	70.8	221
Pennsylvania State University	USA	69.1	290
RAS - P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology	Russia	68.8	210
Rutgers - The State University of New Jersey, New Brunswick	USA	68.2	210
University of Oxford	UK	68.1	266
Victoria University of Wellington	New Zealand	67.7	287
Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland	67.6	265
The University of Tokyo	Japan	66.9	284
Oregon State University	USA	66.8	326
German Aerospace Center	Germany	66.3	178
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich	Switzerland	65.0	282
Helmholtz Centre for Ocean Research Kiel	Germany	63.9	240
University of Wisconsin-Madison	USA	63.2	251
Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences	China	63.1	140
University of California at Santa Cruz	USA	62.6	249
Hokkaido University	Japan	62.6	260
Stanford University	USA	62.1	224
University of Bristol	UK	61.6	255
University of Copenhagen	Denmark	61.1	264
Princeton University	USA	60.8	261
Sorbonne Université	France	60.6	612

Sun Yat-Sen University	China	60.4	215
Southern Marine Science and Engineering Guangdong Laboratory -Guangzhou	China	60.0	216
University of Edinburgh	UK	59.1	254
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande	Brazil	59.0	145
University of Barcelona	Spain	59.0	169
University of Science and Technology of China	China	58.9	171
Cooperative Research Centres Australia	Australia	58.8	397
Université de La Rochelle	France	57.4	296
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	Brazil	56.6	147
University of Leeds	UK	56.5	238
University of Bergen	Norway	56.3	219
The Graduate University for Advanced Studies	Japan	55.5	272
University of Adelaide	Australia	55.1	185
Centre national d'études spatiales	France	54.8	691
Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	Brazil	54.4	159
University of Western Australia	Australia	53.8	179
Beijing Normal University	China	53.7	193
University of California at Irvine	USA	53.6	227
University of Maine	USA	53.5	171
Durham University	UK	52.4	188
University of Exeter	UK	52.3	223
University of Texas at Austin	USA	52.2	203
Museo Argentino de Ciencias Naturales Bernardino Rivadavia	Argentina	51.9	139
University of Hawai'i at Mānoa	USA	51.6	231
University of Hamburg	Germany	51.5	164
Norwegian Polar Institute	Norway	51.3	230
Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro	Brazil	51.2	143
National Antarctic Scientific Center Of Ukraine	Ukraine	51.1	169
University of Waikato	New Zealand	51.0	167
University of Genoa	Italy	50.8	162
China University of Geosciences, Wuhan	China	50.6	148
Université Paris Cité	France	50.3	665
Imperial College London	UK	50.2	233

Table A2. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised and full counting) by institution, total 2022-2024 and sorted by fractionalised counting. Only the largest institutions, in terms of publication output (fractionalised counts), are listed.

Institution	Country	Number of publications (fractionalised)	Number of publications (full counting)
British Antarctic Survey	UK	169.7	640
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China	China	154.3	398
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	135.8	333
University of Tasmania	Australia	126.4	418
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	122.9	536
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	112.1	347
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	96.7	270
Ocean University of China	China	96.7	185
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Res	Germany	89.5	380
CNRS	France	86.0	664
Shanghai Ocean University	China	81.2	129
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	64.8	75
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	63.4	219
Polar Research Institute of China	China	63.2	200
Tongji University	China	60.3	120
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	59.2	219
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	56.8	252
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	55.2	217
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	54.8	229
University of California at San Diego	USA	51.3	212
CSIRO	Australia	48.9	187
University of Washington	USA	47.5	156
Wuhan University	China	46.4	92
Southern Marine Science & Engineering Guangdong Lab - Guanzhou	China	44.1	152
University of New South Wales	Australia	43.0	142
Columbia University	USA	40.3	176
CSIC	Spain	40.3	220
Sun Yat-Sen University	China	40.1	135
University of Cape Town	South Africa	38.9	118
Institut de recherche pour le développement	France	37.8	398
Utrecht University	Netherlands	37.1	129
University of Cambridge	UK	37.0	125
University of Otago	New Zealand	36.9	119
St. Petersburg State University	Russia	35.2	80
Australian National University	Australia	34.8	127
National Centre for Antarctic & Ocean Research	India	34.7	112
University of Bremen	Germany	34.3	154

Research Organisation of Information and Systems, National Institute of Polar Research	Japan	33.5	154
Ministry of Earth Sciences	India	32.9	105
Lomonosov Moscow State University	Russia	31.8	70
Universidad de Magallanes	Chile	30.7	118
University of Canterbury	New Zealand	30.4	105
California Institute of Technology	USA	30.1	130
NIWA	New Zealand	30.0	117
Chinese Academy of Fishery Sciences	China	29.8	64
Universidade de São Paulo	Brazil	29.6	96
Shanghai Jiao Tong University	China	29.2	89
Masaryk University	Czech Rep	28.5	70
University of Southampton	UK	28.5	162
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Argentina	28.5	95
Monash University	Australia	28.0	81
Bulgarian Academy of Sciences	Bulgaria	27.7	45
United States Department of Energy	USA	27.7	178
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	Ukraine	27.7	80
University of Melbourne	Australia	27.6	76
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	USA	27.4	125
Ministerio de Planificación, Chile	Chile	27.2	127
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina	25.8	80
RAS - P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology	Russia	25.8	90
National Center for Atmospheric Research	USA	25.5	121
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA	25.3	106
Universidad de Chile	Chile	25.2	102
Polish Academy of Sciences	Poland	24.9	100
Northumbria University	UK	24.7	93
Universidad Austral de Chile	Chile	24.5	103
Hokkaido University	Japan	24.5	98
China University of Geosciences, Wuhan	China	24.3	76
University of Pretoria	South Africa	24.1	76
Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology	Japan	23.9	98
Ohio State University	USA	23.3	105
Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	Brazil	23.2	80
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	Brazil	23.0	63
CAS - Institute of Atmospheric Physics	China	22.9	112
Universidad de Concepción	Chile	22.6	105
National Oceanography Centre	UK	22.4	129
Xiamen University	China	22.2	61
Universidad de la República	Uruguay	22.2	45
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	USA	22.2	92
University of Johannesburg	South Africa	22.1	117
University of Oslo	Norway	21.9	66
University of Genoa	Italy	21.9	63
The University of Tokyo	Japan	21.7	103
National Antarctic Scientific Center Of Ukraine	Ukraine	21.7	77
Ministry of Agriculture of the People's Republic of China	China	21.6	61

Victoria University of Wellington	New Zealand	21.4	96
China University of Geosciences, Beijing	China	21.4	58
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich	Switzerland	20.9	108
Stanford University	USA	20.8	75
University of Copenhagen	Denmark	20.7	96
Princeton University	USA	20.5	88
University of Edinburgh	UK	20.1	86
The Graduate University for Advanced Studies	Japan	20.0	100
University of East Anglia	UK	19.9	79
Universidade Federal do Rio de Janeiro	Brazil	19.7	64
Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology	USA	19.4	96
University of Science and Technology of China	China	19.4	63
University of Siena	Italy	19.0	60
Pennsylvania State University	USA	18.8	109
University of Hamburg	Germany	18.8	62
Stony Brook University	USA	18.8	62
University of California at Santa Cruz	USA	18.6	85
Nanjing University of Information Science & Technology	China	18.5	55
Istanbul Technical University	Turkey	18.5	33
German Aerospace Center	Germany	18.2	52
University of Western Australia	Australia	18.2	56
University of Oxford	UK	18.2	85
Seoul National University	South Korea	18.0	55
Oregon State University	USA	18.0	106
Delft University of Technology	Netherlands	17.9	55
China Meteorological Administration	China	17.8	52
Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile	Chile	17.6	72
Sorbonne Université	France	17.4	179
Zhejiang University	China	17.3	49
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande	Brazil	17.2	47
University of Bristol	UK	16.8	66
University of Bergen	Norway	16.7	72
CAS - Institute of Oceanology	China	16.6	74
Texas A&M University	USA	16.6	64
Universidade Federal de Viçosa	Brazil	16.5	44
University of Waikato	New Zealand	16.5	49
Nanjing University	USA	16.2	54
Beijing Normal University	China	16.1	64
University of Exeter	UK	16.1	70

Table A3. Number of top-quartile Antarctic publications (Q1) (fractionalised and whole counts) for the largest institutions in terms of publication output. Total figures for the 2022-2024 period and sorted by fractionalised counting.

Institution	Country	Number of articles (fractionalised)	Number of articles (full counting)	Q1 ratio
British Antarctic Survey	UK	101.2	403	0.61
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	71.7	345	0.60
University of Tasmania	Australia	68.6	270	0.61
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Rep of China	China	68.5	214	0.47
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Res	Germany	63.5	278	0.72
Ocean University of China	China	50.6	115	0.53
CNRS	France	48.7	436	0.58
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	46.0	144	0.48
University of California at San Diego	USA	44.9	173	0.88
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	41.4	190	0.74
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	40.7	169	0.74
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	36.3	131	0.60
University of Washington	USA	35.7	124	0.77
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	35.0	38	0.55
University of New South Wales	Australia	33.8	109	0.82
CSIRO	Australia	33.0	138	0.69
Columbia University	USA	32.8	129	0.82
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	32.2	143	0.60
Southern Marine Science and Engineering Guangdong Laboratory - Guanzhou	China	30.2	107	0.71
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	29.2	135	0.56
Utrecht University	Netherlands	28.4	105	0.77
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	28.2	114	0.26
Polar Research Institute of China	China	27.7	101	0.46
Tongji University	China	27.3	65	0.49
Wuhan University	China	27.2	57	0.59
Sun Yat-Sen University	China	26.5	98	0.69
Institut de recherche pour le développement	France	25.9	286	0.70
CSIC	Spain	25.7	147	0.66
University of Bremen	Germany	25.4	117	0.75
Australian National University	Australia	25.1	96	0.72
University of Cambridge	UK	24.8	92	0.71
University of Otago	New Zealand	23.8	84	0.66
National Center for Atmospheric Research	USA	23.6	112	0.76
Northumbria University	UK	21.6	83	0.87
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	USA	21.5	98	0.79
United States Department of Energy	USA	21.3	113	0.78
University of Cape Town	South Africa	21.2	74	0.56
California Institute of Technology	USA	21.1	92	0.73

University of Southampton	UK	19.3	116	0.68
Shanghai Ocean University	China	18.7	44	0.27
Monash University	Australia	18.4	64	0.72
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA	18.1	62	0.72
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	18.1	67	0.14
Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology	Japan	17.6	72	0.74
University of Canterbury	New Zealand	17.3	55	0.61
NIWA	New Zealand	16.9	69	0.58
University of Edinburgh	UK	16.8	73	0.83
Princeton University	USA	16.8	73	0.89
Universidad de Concepción	Chile	16.8	79	0.74
Swiss Federal Institute of Technology Zurich	Switzerland	16.7	86	0.80
CAS - Institute of Atmospheric Physics	China	16.2	86	0.73
Hokkaido University	Japan	16.1	65	0.65
University of Melbourne	Australia	16.0	51	0.67
University of East Anglia	UK	15.6	66	0.83
National Oceanography Centre	UK	15.5	93	0.69
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	USA	15.3	58	0.69
Stanford University	USA	15.2	49	0.73
China University of Geosciences, Wuhan	China	14.9	52	0.62
Research Organisation of Information and Systems, National Institute of Polar Research	Japan	13.9	77	0.42
Shanghai Jiao Tong University	China	13.4	50	0.49
Delft University of Technology	Netherlands	13.2	41	0.74

Table A4. Number of Antarctic publications (fractionalised) and field-weighted citation impact for the largest institutions in terms of publication output ,2020–2023, sorted by field-weighted citation impact.

Institution	Country	Number of articles (fractionalised)	Field-weighted citation impact
Utrecht University	Netherlands	48.3	1.81
University of New South Wales	Australia	62.1	1.74
Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology	USA	30.0	1.70
NASA Goddard Space Flight Center	USA	31.6	1.64
University of Washington	USA	70.7	1.64
CSIRO	Australia	68.3	1.62
National Center for Atmospheric Research	USA	45.3	1.58
National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration	USA	83.1	1.55
Universidad de Chile	Chile	35.5	1.55
University of Canterbury	New Zealand	50.4	1.53
Institut de recherche pour le développement	France	53.7	1.52
Columbia University	USA	68.8	1.50
California Institute of Technology	USA	44.5	1.50
University of Southampton	UK	37.5	1.44
Universidad de Concepción	Chile	36.9	1.39
British Antarctic Survey	UK	238.5	1.37
Victoria University of Wellington	New Zealand	35.0	1.34
University of California at San Diego	USA	78.2	1.33
University of Melbourne	Australia	38.5	1.33
Woods Hole Oceanographic Institution	USA	33.7	1.31
Massachusetts Institute of Technology	USA	33.5	1.31
Monash University	Australia	39.3	1.28
Oregon State University	USA	31.1	1.28
Pennsylvania State University	USA	33.5	1.27
German Aerospace Center	Germany	30.3	1.26
Australian National University	Australia	49.2	1.22
Dalian Polytechnic University	China	54.7	1.21
University of Tasmania	Australia	175.2	1.21
CNRS	France	126.4	1.21
University of Bremen	Germany	56.4	1.18
United States Department of Energy	USA	36.1	1.18
CSIC	Spain	57.6	1.11
Australian Antarctic Division	Australia	78.4	1.11
University of Colorado Boulder	USA	91.3	1.11
Alfred Wegener Institute - Helmholtz Centre for Polar and Marine Research	Germany	143.4	1.10
Japan Agency for Marine-Earth Science and Technology	Japan	39.7	1.08
University of Cape Town	South Africa	44.0	1.08
NIWA	New Zealand	46.0	1.02
University of Cambridge	UK	50.3	1.02

Universidad Austral de Chile	Chile	47.8	0.98
Ohio State University	USA	34.2	0.91
University of Otago	New Zealand	47.5	0.88
Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais	Brazil	32.0	0.87
University of Pretoria	South Africa	37.4	0.84
Hokkaido University	Japan	34.3	0.84
Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	159.7	0.83
National Research Council of Italy	Italy	76.7	0.82
The University of Tokyo	Japan	34.5	0.82
Southern Marine Science and Engineering Guangdong Laboratory - Guanzhou	China	42.9	0.81
University of Chinese Academy of Sciences	China	65.6	0.81
Universidade de São Paulo	Brazil	44.4	0.78
Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas	Argentina	157.6	0.78
Ocean University of China	China	119.2	0.77
Universidad Nacional de La Plata	Argentina	36.2	0.76
National Centre for Antarctic & Ocean Research	India	53.8	0.75
Universidad de Magallanes	Chile	47.8	0.73
Research Organisation of Information and Systems, National Institute of Polar Research	Japan	53.7	0.71
Ministry of Earth Sciences	India	42.7	0.69
Universidad de Buenos Aires	Argentina	35.4	0.69
University of Science and Technology of China	China	31.5	0.68
Tongji University	China	62.4	0.62
RAS - P.P. Shirshov Institute of Oceanology	Russia	42.1	0.61
Ministry of Natural Resources of the People's Republic of China	China	177.5	0.59
Korea Polar Research Institute	South Korea	128.5	0.57
Masaryk University	Czech Republic	41.3	0.57
Polar Research Institute of China	China	75.8	0.50
Shanghai Ocean University	China	100.8	0.49
St. Petersburg State University	Russia	70.1	0.49
Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul	Brazil	34.3	0.49
Russian Academy of Sciences	Russia	207.1	0.46
National Antarctic Scientific Center Of Ukraine	Ukraine	38.1	0.45
Wuhan University	China	72.4	0.43
National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine	Ukraine	43.4	0.37
Lomonosov Moscow State University	Russia	41.5	0.30

Antarctic Research Trends Report 2025

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“THROUGH DATA, PATTERNS, AND CONNECTIONS, THIS REPORT REVEALS HOW ANTARCTIC RESEARCH FORMS A SINGLE GLOBAL FABRIC OF COLLABORATION. BEYOND MEASURING OUTPUT, THE REPORT MAPS THE SHARED PURSUIT OF UNDERSTANDING A CHANGING PLANET — WHERE EVERY CITATION BECOMES A LINK IN THE NETWORK OF KNOWLEDGE THAT SHAPES OUR COMMON FUTURE.”

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THIS BIBLIOMETRIC REPORT PROVIDES A COMPREHENSIVE ANALYSIS OF THE GLOBAL LANDSCAPE OF ANTARCTIC RESEARCH. BY MAPPING COLLABORATIONS, PUBLICATION TRENDS, AND SCIENTIFIC IMPACT, IT ILLUSTRATES HOW PARTNERSHIPS AND SHARED INFRASTRUCTURES DRIVE DISCOVERY AND INNOVATION ACROSS DISCIPLINES.

BEYOND OFFERING AN EVIDENCE-BASED OVERVIEW, THE REPORT INVITES REFLECTION ON THE STRUCTURES THAT ENABLE RESEARCH EXCELLENCE. IT IDENTIFIES OPPORTUNITIES FOR STRONGER COORDINATION, HIGHLIGHTS EMERGING THEMATIC AREAS, AND SUPPORTS INFORMED DECISIONS FOR UNIVERSITIES, FUNDING AGENCIES, AND POLICYMAKERS SEEKING TO STRENGTHEN THE COLLECTIVE IMPACT OF ANTARCTIC SCIENCE.

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